

DroneWaste dataset for waste recognition in drone imagery

Luca Morandini ^a Andrea Diecidue ^{a*} Thanos Petsanis ^{b,c}
Enrico Targhini ^a Georgios Karatzinis ^c Giacomo Boracchi ^a
Elias B. Kosmatopoulos ^{b,c} Piero Fraternali ^a
Athanasios Ch. Kapoutsis ^{b,c}

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^a Politecnico di Milano, Department of Electronics, Information, and Bioengineering, via Ponzio 34/5, Milan 20133, Italy

^b Democritus University of Thrace, Department of Electrical Engineering, University in Xanthi, Greece

^c Information Technologies Institute, The Centre for Research & Technology Hellas, Thessaloniki, Greece

Abstract

Illegal waste disposal has a negative impact on the environment and people's quality of life. Drone imagery enables law enforcement authorities to efficiently assess the environmental impact during on-site inspections of suspicious landfill sites. Automated tools based on Deep Learning techniques can then quickly analyze aerial images to recognize several waste materials and classify their hazard level. However, large high-quality datasets are required for training and testing waste recognition models. Currently, no such datasets are publicly available, which limits the development of accurate waste identification algorithms. This paper presents DroneWaste, a dataset of aerial images extracted from orthomosaics that are reconstructed from drone-collected imagery. The dataset is a collection of 4993 images of 17 solid waste dumps that contain 20 different types of materials. The DroneWaste dataset is publicly accessible from the [Zenodo repository](#). Technical validation proves that the dataset can be used for building object detection models able to recognize several types of waste in aerial imagery.

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1 Background & Summary

Illegal waste dumping is a form of environmental crime with severe impacts on ecosystems, such as increased pollution, loss of biodiversity, and risks to human health. This phenomenon is increasingly recognized to have significant adverse effects on the economy and on the ecology on a global scale [1, 2]. Many illicit waste management organizations resort to illegal dumping or waste trafficking to minimize costs at the expense of environmental integrity and public health [3]. To counteract this escalating problem, Law Enforcement Agencies (LEAs) and Environmental Protection Agencies (EPAs) are required to identify potential illegal waste sites on a large-scale territory. When illegal activities are discovered, accurate forensic evidence must be collected to prosecute the involved criminals. A factor highly relevant to the definition of the criminal charge is the type of waste improperly treated. The penalties become more severe when toxic or dangerous substances are present, due to the high risks they pose to the environment and public health. The list of materials classified as extremely hazardous is specified by European Standards [4], including items such as asbestos slabs, hydrofluorocarbons, and toxic chemicals.

On-site inspections of suspicious sites are expensive, require significant human effort, and can threaten the safety of the involved personnel when hazardous materials are present. Furthermore, illegal waste dumps are often located in inaccessible and remote areas far from densely populated

*Corresponding author: andrea.diecidue@polimi.it

places. Due to these constraints, combined with the vastness of the territory to be monitored, LEAs often conduct investigations using drones for imagery acquisition. Recent advances in Computer Vision (CV) and Deep Learning (DL) offer new opportunities for automating waste identification in images. Modern image analysis methods can be applied to satellite images to locate suspicious sites in vast regions [5]. Then, drone surveys support EPA inspectors in investigating the most critical waste dumping sites, thus enhancing the overall efficiency of the territory monitoring activity. However, modern DL models require large annotated datasets to learn the peculiar features of materials and recognize waste accumulations. In recent years, various datasets have been introduced in the waste detection literature, which utilize different data sources, including satellites, drones, and smartphones. Table 1 provides a comparison of the most relevant waste detection datasets.

Satellite imagery for waste identification has attracted increasing interest, mainly due to the availability of high-resolution images covering vast areas. Several publicly available datasets for solid waste detection in satellite images are mentioned in the scientific works. Solid Waste Aerial Detection (SWAD) [6] is a collection of satellite images encompassing urban, rural, and mountainous scenes, which are annotated with single-class bounding boxes delineating solid waste objects. Global Dumpsite Test Data (GDTD) dataset [7] includes numerous illegal dumps and a few regulated landfills. The employed satellite imagery has a Ground Sampling Distance (GSD) ranging from $0.3m$ to $1m$. The relevant sites are annotated with bounding boxes labeled with one of four categories (domestic, construction, agricultural, or covered waste). The RS4SW dataset [8] employs Google Earth images ($0.5m$ GSD) of three urban areas: Langfang (China), Faridabad (India), and Tezoyuca (Mexico). Each image is categorized as portraying solid waste (SW) or other non-solid waste (non-SW) scenes. The waste annotated in this dataset comprises industrial materials, domestic litter in residential zones, and construction and demolition debris. The Construction Waste Landfill Dataset (CWLD) [9] includes Gaofen-2 satellite and Google Earth images of Beijing’s Changping and Daxing districts. It focuses on construction waste and supports semantic segmentation tasks, for which pixel-level annotation masks are provided. Finally, AerialWaste [5] comprises more than 10,000 aerial images with different sources: AGEA orthophotos, WorldView-3 satellite, and Google Earth images. The annotations provide binary image-level labels that specify the presence/absence of waste, and a subset of images is further tagged with 22 distinct waste materials. Remote sensing and satellite imagery are useful for scanning large areas and identifying suspicious locations. However, the provided GSD, ranging from $1.8m$ [6] to $20cm$ [5], is insufficient for the fine-grained identification of most waste materials.

The adoption of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) [10] and the recent advances in DL models and CV techniques have provided LEAs and EPAs with effective tools for close-view investigation of the suspicious sites, once identified with satellite image analysis. The employed drones are equipped with a variety of sensors (e.g., high-resolution cameras, multispectral sensors, LiDAR, and GNSS-RTK), which support the detailed characterization of materials and the collection of forensic evidence from the inspected sites. A few datasets of UAV images depicting urban litter in the wild have been proposed in the literature. UAVVaste [11] comprises 772 low-altitude drone images of urban and natural scenes (e.g., streets, parks, lawns), annotated with 3700 instance masks and bounding boxes for a single *rubbish* class. However, this dataset includes samples of sparse small litter that are easily distinguishable from the surrounding environment. Therefore, they are not representative of the large accumulations of waste typical of illegal landfills. The SUIRD dataset [12] consists of 628 images collected from low-altitude UAV flights, which are augmented to create a more extensive training dataset. Accumulated or scattered garbage is annotated with single-class bounding boxes, but the waste categories are not provided. Finally, the RSD dataset [13] provides 2600 drone images annotated at the pixel level with three generic waste categories (construction, household, mixed). However, this level of detail is not relevant for training DL models to recognize a wide spectrum of waste materials. UAV images are geometrically corrected and stitched together to generate images with a GSD of 3.8 cm/px , which prevents the identification of small items.

The perspective offered by low-altitude UAV flights enables the precise identification and classification of a wide range of materials. However, publicly available drone-captured datasets provide a single waste class [11, 12] or a limited range of generic waste categories [13]. Therefore, these datasets are unsuitable for waste detection in landfills that include a wide range of materials captured in real-world scenarios.

Besides the typical satellite and drone datasets, various studies introduced specialized data collections to recognize specific waste materials in images captured with hand-held cameras or smartphones. The TACO dataset [14] comprises 1500 high-resolution images of urban and natural scenes annotated with 4784 instance-level segmentation masks using a taxonomy of 60 fine-grained classes grouped into 28 super-categories. Early efforts such as TrashNet [15] and WaDaBa [16] provide a few thousand handheld photographs of common disposable objects. TrashNet includes

2527 images collected with smartphones that depict six different types of garbage (glass, paper, cardboard, plastic, metal, trash). WaDaBa includes 4000 images of plastic waste, generated by capturing 100 objects from 40 different views under controlled conditions. OpenLitterMap [17] is a continuously growing, crowd-sourced collection of over 100k geotagged images captured by smartphone cameras, containing a wide range of individual litter samples in urban environments. Finally, indoor waste recognition is addressed by the MJU-Waste dataset [18], which provides 2475 waste images captured with an RGB-Depth camera and annotated with instance-level segmentation masks.

However, hand-held and smartphone cameras are ineffective for simulating the characteristics of LEA’s drone flights, which are therefore inadequate for waste identification from UAV imagery due to significant differences in perspective and resolution.

Table 1: Description of datasets for waste recognition across different spatial scales, from camera-level to UAV and satellite-based imagery. For each dataset, the supported tasks are reported (OD: Object Detection, IS: Instance Segmentation, SS: Semantic Segmentation, BC: Binary Classification, SLC: Single-Label Classification, MCL: Multi-Label Classification).

Input	Dataset	Classes	Images	Task	Sources
Satellites	SWAD [6]	1	1996	OD	WorldView-2, SPOT
	GDTD [7]	4	2219	OD	Different satellites
	RS4SW [8]	2	3680	BC	Google Earth
	CWLD [9]	4	3653	SS	Gaofen-2, Google Earth
	AerialWaste [5]	22	10,434	IS	WorldView-3, Google Earth, aerial orthophotos
UAV	UAVWaste [11]	1	772	IS, OD	UAV
	SUIRD [12]	1	628	OD	UAV
	RSD [13]	3	2600	SS	UAV
	DroneWaste (Ours)	20	4993	IS, OD	UAV
Ground sensors	TACO [14]	60	4784	IS	Smartphone camera
	TrashNet [15]	6	2527	SLC	Smartphone camera
	WaDaBa [16]	6	4000	SLC	Digital camera
	OpenLitterMap [17]	100+	100,000+	MLC	Smartphone camera
	MJU-Waste [18]	1	2475	IS	RGB-D camera

The detection and classification of waste instances is a challenging task due to the broad range of heterogeneous materials, their different shapes and textures, and the potential confusion with ordinary non-waste objects. DL algorithms require a substantial amount of high-quality annotated images to effectively recognize the distinctive features of waste materials. Currently, the lack of UAV-captured waste datasets in real-world scenarios hinders the research towards scalable and accurate waste recognition methods that can effectively assist LEAs and EPAs in their inspection activities.

The contribution of this work is the DroneWaste dataset, a professionally curated set of UAV images for waste recognition, which is constructed on the following principles:

1. 4993 images are extracted from orthomosaics generated on 17 sites representing different scenarios and environments.
2. The average orthomosaic GSD in most sites is 2 cm/px, with some exceptions up to 2.8 cm/px.
3. Images are professionally annotated with 5135 waste instances that cover 20 waste types that include the majority of materials typically present in landfills.
4. Annotations are curated by professional photo-interpreters specialized in using UAV images for dump site inspection.
5. Each waste instance in an image is annotated with a polygon delimiting the boundaries and a bounding box that contains the waste object.
6. The dataset adheres to the standard COCO format [19].

An initial version of the DroneWaste dataset has been employed in our preliminary work [20] where an Object Detection (OD) network was trained to recognize 7 types of waste. Results showed that OD is effective, especially in recognizing regularly shaped waste materials (such as

Textile, Pallets and Tyres), with the best model achieving AP scores above 60%. The work also proposed a practical DL-based pipeline that supports the investigation processes of LEAs and EPAs in analyzing illegal waste sites.

2 Methods

The DroneWaste dataset comprises images of real-world landfills and industrial waste disposal sites. The on-site UAV surveys were performed in Italy by ARPA Lombardia, a regional EPA, and in Greece by CERTH, a non-profit organization supervised by the General Secretariat for Research and Technology (GSRT) of the Hellenic Republic and one of the largest research centers in Greece. Commercial drones, described in Section 2.1, were employed to capture the images of 17 waste dumping sites.

Figure 1 illustrates the procedure for generating the DroneWaste dataset. For each inspected location, images acquired during a survey are processed to generate an orthomosaic, which is then manually annotated to create the site ground truth. From each orthomosaic, the dataset images are extracted and labeled by mapping the ground truth annotations previously defined on the entire orthomosaic. A final filtering step removes the annotations of partially visible waste instances.

Figure 1: The DroneWaste dataset creation workflow. Drone-acquired images are combined to generate an orthomosaic that covers the waste dumping site. Each orthomosaic is manually annotated to create the site ground truth. Images that compose the DroneWaste dataset are extracted using a sliding window approach.

2.1 Data acquisition

The 17 UAV surveys that are included in the DroneWaste dataset capture real-world waste dumping activities in diverse scenarios and landscapes. The images from 6 locations show industrial sites where both authorized materials and illegal waste are present. Another 8 scenarios represent open landfills in rural areas characterized by the dumping of mixed waste or construction material. Finally, 3 locations are characterized by accumulations of waste scattered over a large area. Table 2 specifies the characteristics of the sites included in the dataset.

Data collection flights were conducted using two commercial drones: *DJI Phantom 4 Pro* and *DJI Mavic 2 Enterprise Advanced*. The *Phantom 4 Pro* drone mounts a *DJI FC6310* camera that has a 1-inch CMOS sensor (20 MP, 24 mm equivalent focal length), an adjustable aperture (f/2.8–f/11), and wide ISO and shutter speed ranges. The *Mavic 2 Enterprise Advanced* drone is equipped with a *DJI FC2453* camera, using a 1/2-inch CMOS sensor (48 MP, 24 mm equivalent focal length, f/2.8 fixed aperture). A commercial path planning software, *DJI Pilot*, is used for mission planning. The adopted flight paths, tailored for photogrammetry applications, are standard grid formations with -90° pitch angle (i.e., the camera pointing down towards the ground). A

Table 2: Summary of the most relevant site properties. For each site, the number of images and annotations in the DroneWaste dataset is reported. The *Materials* column specifies the number of waste materials present at each site. Most orthomosaics are generated with a GSD of 2 cm/px. The reported GSD varies because, in those scenarios, it was not possible to collect enough images to produce an orthomosaic with higher resolution. The *Area* column reports the area in m^2 of each generated orthomosaic.

Site ID	Scenario	Location	Area	GSD	Images	Annotations	Materials
Site 1	open landfill	Greece	22,200	2.3	119	75	10
Site 2	open landfill	Italy	18,300	2	130	100	12
Site 3	scattered waste	Italy	95,500	2	698	243	14
Site 4	industrial site	Italy	25,100	2	182	461	12
Site 5	industrial site	Italy	30,000	2	217	649	18
Site 6	scattered waste	Greece	227,400	2.8	813	252	13
Site 7	open landfill	Greece	1300	2.4	6	10	2
Site 8	industrial site	Italy	28,800	2	210	173	11
Site 9	open landfill	Greece	11,800	2	83	526	11
Site 10	open landfill	Greece	3800	2.3	17	25	5
Site 11	open landfill	Italy	113,100	2	825	173	11
Site 12	industrial site	Italy	26,100	2	186	540	10
Site 13	industrial site	Italy	24,200	2	169	658	14
Site 14	industrial site	Italy	40,400	2	279	792	14
Site 15	open landfill	Greece	22,600	2.2	136	115	8
Site 16	scattered waste	Italy	115,600	1.9	848	186	15
Site 17	open landfill	Greece	15,900	2.4	75	157	5

standardized data acquisition protocol was used across all sites, and several photogrammetry best practices were implemented to improve the quality of the reconstructed orthomosaic. In particular, the frontlap between images is kept constant at 80%, the sidelap at 70%, and dynamic elements (e.g., moving vehicles or people) were avoided. The flight altitude ranges between 15 and 100 meters, depending on the area size and the obstacles. In smaller landfill sites, a higher number of low-altitude UAV images can be collected to cover the surveyed area. In contrast, at larger dumping sites with obstructions (e.g., buildings), low-altitude flights are forbidden due to the risk of collision.

Aerial images were captured with the RGB camera at full sensor resolution. Each image embeds several metadata in EXIF format, such as GPS coordinates, camera gimbal orientation, and lens properties. This information is exploited during the orthomosaic generation process by photogrammetry software to provide a rough initialization for all camera poses, improving the reconstruction quality.

2.2 Orthomosaic generation

The UAV images collected during a flight are combined using photogrammetry software to generate a georeferenced orthomosaic of the surveyed site. An orthomosaic is a large image with high detail and resolution, assembled from many smaller UAV images. A georeferenced orthomosaic is a special case where each pixel of the output map is associated with a location with known coordinates. Any photogrammetry software would be suitable for the task. Specifically, this work uses OpenDroneMap (ODM) [21], an open-source tool for drone image processing, which applies several processing phases to correct distortions in UAV images, create a 3D reconstruction, and generate a georeferenced orthomosaic covering the entire scene. The image is orthorectified, meaning that distortions and perspectives are removed from the resulting image.

The DroneWaste orthomosaic maps are generated with a GSD of 2 cm/px. This value represents a trade-off between image resolution and computational requirements. High spatial resolution enables the discrimination of fine-grained textures in waste materials. Yet, an excessively high resolution increases the computational and storage requirements, making it impractical for large survey areas.

Table 2 reports the GSD of each site orthomosaic. For most sites, the target GSD of 2 cm/px is reached during the generation process. However, in some scenarios, it was not possible to collect enough images to produce an orthomosaic with a higher GSD, so some orthomosaics are reconstructed with a slightly lower spatial resolution. The maximum (worst) GSD is 2.8 cm/px

for *Site 6*. Figure 2 illustrates examples of tiles extracted from the generated orthomosaics. The captured scenarios are very heterogeneous and reflect the range of waste disposal sites and of materials composing the DroneWaste dataset.

Figure 2: Examples of tiles extracted from the DroneWaste orthomosaics, along with the color-coded legend of the annotated waste categories.

2.3 Data annotation

The produced orthomosaics cover extensive areas with high spatial resolution, resulting in a significant image size. For example, *Site 6*, the largest orthomosaic included in the DroneWaste dataset, has a size of $19,450 \times 16,491$ px and occupies 686 MB of disk space. Such dimensions are too large for commercial annotation tools, typically employed to label smaller images. To enable the use of standard annotation tools, a site orthomosaic is decomposed into smaller overlapping tiles that cover a fixed area of the ground. Tiles with a size of 40×40 m are extracted using a sliding window approach with an overlap of 5 m between adjacent tiles. The tiles were manually annotated using Roboflow [22], a commercial annotation tool that enables collaborative workflows. The annotation process utilizes a *Smart Polygon* functionality, which is a semi-automatic tool that leverages the Segment Anything Model (SAM) [23] to quickly segment individual objects in the scene. SAM enables the rapid definition of polygons around waste instances by selecting a few points on the image. The automatically created polygons can be manually corrected to better fit the shape of the waste instance and the waste class is added to each polygon by the expert annotator.

Table 3 lists the 20 categories considered in the DroneWaste dataset. Each waste class is associated with a *European Waste Code* (EWC) [4] to align the annotations with the *European List of Waste* (LoW) defined by the European Commission under Directive 2008/98/EC on waste. The waste categories included in the dataset have been chosen based on the presence of materials in the site surveys. The *Materials* column in Table 2 shows that all locations contain only a subset of the 20 waste categories, resulting in a heterogeneous distribution across sites. The waste classes can be divided into *pile* categories, including materials typically occurring in piles or heaps with irregular boundaries (e.g., *Rubble*, *Mixed items*), and *instance* categories, for which individual waste elements can be recognized (e.g., *Metal barrels*, *Pallets*, *Tyres*). Note that the dataset includes instances of the class *Asbestos*, a material commonly used in the roofs of old buildings, which needs to be identified due to its high toxicity even when present in the form of roof cover and not as proper waste.

The manual annotation phase was conducted by a team of 7 researchers and 2 investigators from an EPA, all experienced in recognizing waste from UAV imagery. Since multiple annotators from different organizations were involved, the procedure was standardized to ensure consistency. Guidelines were established to provide a brief description and examples of each waste category, and

Table 3: The list of 20 categories of waste annotated in the DroneWaste dataset. Each class is assigned an EWC code to uniquely identify the waste material.

Color	Category	Type	EWC
●	Rubble	pile	12.61 Soils
●	Construction and demolition materials	pile	12.11 Concrete, bricks and gypsum waste
●	Asphalt milling	pile	12.12 Waste hydrocarbonised road-surfacing material
●	Excavation materials	pile	12.31 Waste of naturally occurring minerals
●	Appliances	instance	08.21 Discarded major household equipment
●	Electronic equipment	instance	08.23 Other discarded electrical and electronic equipment
●	Furniture	instance	10.11 Household wastes
●	Metal barrels	instance	06.31 Mixed metallic packaging
●	Plastic packaging	instance	07.41 Plastic packaging wastes
●	Wood	pile	07.53 Other wood wastes
●	Pallets	instance	07.51 Wood packaging
●	Scrap	pile	06.11 Ferrous metal waste and scrap
●	Plastic	pile	07.42 Other plastic wastes
●	Vehicles	instance	08.12 Other discarded vehicles
●	Tyres	instance	07.31 Used tyres
●	Paper	instance	07.2 Paper and cardboard wastes
●	Foundry	pile	12.42 Slags and ashes from thermal treatment and combustion
●	Asbestos	instance	12.21 Asbestos wastes
●	Textile	instance	07.6 Textiles wastes
●	Mixed items	pile	10.2 Mixed and undifferentiated materials

the annotations created by a team member were reviewed by a different annotator to minimise user bias. After the manual data labelling phase, all polygons annotated on the tiles were projected onto the orthomosaic. When a larger waste element was not fully contained within a single tile, polygons with the same category from nearby tiles were combined into a single polygon that covered the entire waste instance. Further annotation validation identified and resolved inconsistent cases, such as:

- Duplicate annotations on the same tile (e.g., nested annotations of the same class).
- Overlapping annotations with different categories on the same tile.
- Overlapping annotations with different categories on adjacent tiles (e.g., incorrectly classified partially visible waste instances).

Such conflicts were identified by an automatic script and resolved manually. The final ground truth of each site includes a series of polygons associated with a waste category and georeferenced to the orthomosaic coordinates. Figure 3 shows all the orthomosaics included in the dataset. Some of them cover an extensive area while others (e.g., *Site 7*, *Site 11*) are much smaller. In many cases, the waste is scattered throughout the scene with large areas of waste-free background.

2.4 Dataset preparation

The tiles that compose the DroneWaste dataset have a standard size of 640×640 px, which reflects the typical dimensions used by image analysis models. The sliding window processing step extracts tiles with a 10% overlap between rows and columns to avoid missing objects on the edge of a tile. Images near the orthomosaic border that contained more than 70% black pixels were discarded from the dataset. When using a sliding window, it may happen that only a small portion of a waste instance is visible in a tile. Such partial visibility negatively impacts the waste recognition task, as a detection model may fail to learn relevant features from a reduced portion of a waste instance. Therefore, small partial annotations were removed. The filtering logic differs between *instance* and *pile* waste categories. For *instance* categories, where objects have regular size and shape, samples are kept if a minimum portion of the object remains visible in an image. Category-specific

Figure 3: The full orthomosaics of all the sites included in the DroneWaste dataset.

thresholds were defined empirically by considering the smallest image region still permitting the recognition of an object and the threshold values range from 10% to 20% of the whole object area. For *pile* categories, the area size of annotations varies significantly (piles can range from very small to very large) and therefore a partial heap annotation is filtered out when it represents less than 1% of the whole annotation.

Ultimately, the dataset creation process outputs the ground truth samples of all the 17 sites. Table 2 reports the number of images and of annotated waste elements. Each ground truth sample has a segmentation mask and a bounding box. The full collection of ground truth samples of DroneWaste includes 5135 annotations on 4993 images.

3 Data Record

The DroneWaste dataset is published in a Zenodo repository (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17045558>) and comprises the following artifacts, which constitute the public part of the dataset:

1. Images folder: contains the images extracted from all site orthomosaics. The provided images are not georeferenced because the coordinates are considered sensitive information and have therefore been removed.
2. Dataset ground truth: a JSON file that describes the images and annotations of the dataset using the COCO format. Both segmentation masks and bounding boxes are defined for all annotated waste instances.
3. Information file: general information about the current dataset version. Not relevant for training or evaluating detection models.

Figure 4 illustrates the organization of the DroneWaste dataset directory structure.

Figure 4: Directory structure of the DroneWaste dataset, showing the organization of metadata files and imagery.

Figure 5 illustrates the distribution of the waste categories in the dataset. Although the class distribution may appear imbalanced, several considerations are worth mentioning:

1. Some categories are inherently rare (e.g., *Asphalt milling*, *Foundry* or *Paper*), thus underrepresented in the DroneWaste dataset. Nevertheless, these rare instances have been annotated to enable the development and performance assessment of detection methods with few samples.
2. Categories representing individual items (e.g., *Plastic packaging*, *Tyres*, or *Metal barrels*) often result in many single-object small annotations.
3. Conversely, categories aggregated in piles (e.g., *Rubble* or *Mixed items*) are typically annotated as few large patches covering significant portions of an image.

The difference in distribution between instance and pile classes is also evident in Figure 6, which reports the relative pixel coverage of each class in the images. Items such as *Pallets* and *Textile*, which are typically small and isolated, have a larger number of annotations but cover a smaller area compared to the other classes. On the other hand, *Rubble* or *Mixed items* are often grouped in piles and occupy a larger region of the images. Another material that covers wide areas is *Asbestos* because its instances most often correspond to roofs that span large portions of the image.

Figure 7 presents a site-wise breakdown of the dataset, showing for each location the number of UAV-captured photos compared to the annotated images extracted from the orthomosaic. Each bar is divided into two colors, representing images annotated with at least one waste element and the images that contain only background. The chart also reports the percentage of background-only images to the total number of site images. Images without any visible waste material are

Figure 5: Distribution of the waste categories in the dataset

Figure 6: Mean per-class percentage of image area covered by annotated pixels.

still valuable for tasks such as object detection or semantic segmentation because they enhance the performance of DL models by providing negative samples that represent the background. For this reason, background-only images are retained in the dataset. The dashed line in Figure 7 illustrates the number of UAV images captured during each survey. These are the images that the photogrammetry tool processes to generate the site orthomosaic, as discussed in Section 2.2. The discrepancy between the number of UAV photos and the number of images extracted from the orthomosaic is caused by variations in data acquisition parameters, especially flight altitude. Flights at lower altitudes enable the acquisition of a larger number of high-resolution images, but with significant overlap. For example, for *Site 2*, *Site 9*, *Site 15*, *Site 17*, numerous UAV images are acquired, despite the inspected area being relatively small, as indicated by the small number of images extracted from the orthomosaic. The proposed dataset creation methodology, based on an orthomosaic generation step, facilitates the standardization of the GSD across all sites. Furthermore, the use of a fixed sliding window for extracting images from the orthomosaics eases the calibration of the overlap between the tiles, hence minimizing redundant information.

4 Technical Validation

This Section focuses on assessing the effectiveness of the DroneWaste dataset for training a DL model able to identify waste materials in UAV images.

Figure 7: Images count across all sites. The bar plot shows the distribution of images extracted from the orthomosaic of each site. The blue bar represents images annotated with at least one waste element, while the orange bar counts background-only images. The percentage above the bars indicates the ratio between the number of site images without annotation and the total number of images for that region. The dashed line illustrates the number of UAV images captured at each site.

4.1 Waste detection

In practical applications, a waste detection model supports investigators in identifying hazardous materials and assessing their environmental impact. The waste materials used for the experiments have highly varying sizes. Some waste classes comprise small objects (e.g., *Tyres*, *Metal barrels*), whereas other classes are characterized by large piles (e.g., *Rubble*, *Mixed items*). Therefore, a waste recognition model should implement a multi-scale architecture to identify objects with largely different scales.

In the conducted waste detection experiments, the DroneWaste dataset has been used to fine-tune three state-of-the-art object detection networks, namely, YOLOv8 [24], YOLOv12 [25], and Faster R-CNN [26], which are all pretrained on the COCO dataset [19]. YOLOv8 and Faster R-CNN are among the most popular object detection frameworks with substantially different architectures. YOLOv8 addresses the task as a single regression problem, predicting all object categories and bounding boxes simultaneously in a single pass. Faster R-CNN has a two-stage architecture that identifies regions of interest, which are individually processed by the detection head to classify each object. YOLOv12 is a recent evolution in the YOLO family, which introduced an area attention mechanism applied locally to small image patches. The networks are trained for 300 epochs using early stopping to prevent models from overfitting. All images were retained in the training set, including background-only samples. The latter supports learning relevant background features that the detector should not confuse with waste instances. Several data augmentation techniques (e.g., rotation, shift, flip, scale) were applied to improve the generalization capability of trained object detectors.

4.2 Evaluation procedure

The DroneWaste dataset comprises 17 site surveys with high contextual variance and an unbalanced distribution of waste materials. As discussed in Section 2, some sites mostly contain industrial waste, whereas other landfills are characterized by municipal or construction waste. Therefore, a k-fold cross-validation strategy has been adopted to provide a robust assessment of model performance and generalization capacity. With k-fold cross-validation, the dataset is partitioned into k disjoint subsets and the evaluation procedure is repeated multiple times rather than relying on a single run with a predefined training and test split. In the experiments, each of the 17 sites was treated as a separate fold to prevent data leakage that may occur if a tile from the same site is assigned to both the training and the test sets. At each iteration, the model is trained on $k - 1$ sites and tested on the remaining site. The validation set is defined by randomly sampling

images from the training sites using a stratified strategy to preserve similar category distributions. The procedure is repeated k times, with each site used exactly once as the test set. After each model training, predictions are generated for the test site. Finally, predictions for all 17 sites are aggregated, and the performance is evaluated against the complete dataset ground truth. The performances are quantified using the standard Average Precision (AP) metric with an Intersection over Union (IoU) threshold of 50%. The AP is separately computed for each waste category. The mean AP (mAP) is calculated as the average across all class-wise APs.

4.3 Waste detection benchmark

The conducted experiments exploit DroneWaste to train object detection models able to recognize multiple waste materials in UAV images. However, as illustrated in Section 3, some waste categories (e.g., *Asphalt milling*, *Paper*, *Foundry*) in the DroneWaste dataset have very few samples, which are not sufficient for training a DL model with a supervised learning approach. Therefore, such underrepresented classes are not considered for the evaluation benchmark. Object detection models learn to recognize characteristic features of regular and similar objects, but are less effective on classes with very heterogeneous samples. As discussed in Section 2.3, *pile* categories comprise samples with irregular shapes and blurred boundaries. For this reason, the benchmark evaluation mostly focuses on *instance* categories with regularly shaped waste items. The considered categories are: *Metal barrels*, *Plastic packaging*, *Pallets*, *Vehicles*, *Tyres*, *Asbestos*, *Textile*. However, we also included a subset of the most represented *pile* classes to assess the detection capability on such challenging materials, aiming to provide insights for a broader set of waste categories. The included pile classes are: *Construction and demolition materials*, *Scrap*, *Mixed items*.

Table 4 illustrates the results achieved by YOLOv8, YOLOv12, and Faster R-CNN on the benchmark dataset. The best-performing model is YOLOv12, achieving 38.5% mAP, closely followed by YOLOv8 with 38.2% mAP. The Faster R-CNN network reaches a mAP of 36.5% (2% lower than YOLOv12). All three models obtain good results on regularly shaped waste (*Pallets*, *Tyres*, *Textile*) and materials with distinctive patterns (*Asbestos*). Both YOLO networks achieve promising results on *Metal barrels*, especially YOLOv12 with 50.5% AP, whereas Faster R-CNN has worse performance. All models demonstrate high precision on the *Asbestos* class, indicating that automated tools can consistently and accurately detect such a hazardous material.

Table 4: Object detection benchmark results using baseline models trained on the DroneWaste dataset. Values in bold indicate the highest values among all models.

Category	Type	YOLOv8	YOLOv12	Faster R-CNN
Construction and demolition materials	pile	13.05%	9.25%	8.82%
Metal barrels	instance	37.64%	50.52%	27.60%
Plastic packaging	instance	5.39%	6.46%	11.48%
Pallets	instance	63.69%	67.24%	61.35%
Scrap	pile	14.74%	16.96%	16.41%
Vehicles	instance	5.66%	1.60%	19.71%
Tyres	instance	64.86%	61.08%	56.86%
Asbestos	instance	76.15%	76.91%	73.85%
Textile	instance	78.53%	75.76%	70.16%
Mixed items	pile	22.47%	19.08%	19.37%
mAP	-	38.22%	38.49%	36.56%

Figure 8 compares detections from the three evaluated models on sample images from the DroneWaste dataset. Detection results from YOLOv8 (second column), YOLOv12 (third column), and Faster R-CNN (fourth column) are compared to the ground truth (first column). The displayed predictions are filtered with a confidence threshold of 0.5.

Common and visually distinct objects are well recognized by all models, such as *Asbestos* (Figure 8(A)), *Tyres* (Figure 8(B)), and *Textile* (Figure 8(C)), including smaller isolated instances of *Pallets* in Figure 8(B). Faster R-CNN achieves better performance on the *Plastic packaging* category compared to the YOLO networks. This model is more capable of identifying small isolated plastic bags, as shown in Figure 8(E).

These results demonstrate the effectiveness of the DroneWaste dataset for training object detection models to recognize waste instances in UAV imagery.

Figure 8: Examples of results from the three object detection models on several scenarios with different waste materials. The box color represents the waste category. The first column shows the dataset ground truth. The other columns show predictions from YOLOv8, YOLOv12, and Faster R-CNN, respectively.

However, Table 4 shows that all models have poor detection performance on the *Vehicles* category. Figure 9 illustrates the reason behind such weak detection results, by reporting three examples of this class. Both YOLO models are unable to distinguish between abandoned and damaged cars (Figure 9(F, G)), which are actual waste instances, and operational vehicles (Figure 9(H)), which are often present at many sites but are not annotated as waste. Faster R-CNN achieves better accuracy in recognizing damaged vehicles. However, the AP value on *Vehicles* category remains below 20%, which is attributed to the tendency of over-predicting, as shown in Figure 9(G).

Figure 9: Examples of results on the *Vehicles* category. The box color represents the waste category. The first column shows the dataset ground truth. The other columns show predictions from YOLOv8, YOLOV12, and Faster R-CNN, respectively.

As anticipated, experimental results show that object detection networks struggle with materials that typically occur in piles with irregular shapes and boundaries. This is the case for *Construction and demolition materials*, *Scrap*, and *Mixed items*, as shown in Figure 8(D), where YOLOv8 and Faster R-CNN confuse *Construction and demolition materials* as *Mixed items*. For such heterogeneous materials, a segmentation approach may be better suited. The reason is that semantic segmentation models learn to predict a category for each pixel in the image rather than identifying entire objects.

5 Usage Notes

The DroneWaste dataset is a collection of real-world waste dumping scenarios that can be used for training waste recognition DL models. The goal of this dataset is to promote the development of computer-aided tools that investigators can utilize in practical applications to enhance the efficiency of waste site monitoring.

During the manual labeling process, several measures were adopted to ensure high-quality and consistent annotations across all 17 locations in the dataset. Professional photo-interpreters with experience in waste recognition from UAV imagery have been involved to define the annotation guidelines. Moreover, the work of each annotator was reviewed by another team member to reduce personal bias and increase label coherence.

However, when using the DroneWaste dataset to train waste detectors, a few key aspects implicit in the use case should be considered:

- *Limited scenarios*: Despite a heterogeneous distribution of waste materials across sites, the scenes captured in the dataset are mostly open landfills, industrial sites, or areas with scattered waste.

- *Background-only images prevalence*: As shown in Figure 7, most images capture background scenes without waste materials. However, these images have been included because they represent the distribution of typical scenarios characterized by large empty areas and sparse accumulation of waste material.
- *Different orthomosaic GSD*: Due to limited UAV coverage, a few orthomosaics were generated with a slightly reduced ground resolution compared to the target GSD of 2 cm/px, as shown in Table 2. The GSD of images ranges between 1.9 and 2.8 cm/px across all locations.
- *Categories with few samples*: Some rare materials are represented by a limited number of samples. Such waste categories are included in the dataset for completeness of annotation and to support future research on few-shot detection methods. Moreover, even the underrepresented materials can be used in binary recognition tasks, in which all categories are treated as a single *Waste* super-category.

Several object detection experiments have been conducted on the DroneWaste dataset, with the results reported in Section 4. From an application perspective, the achieved level of automated intelligence has been judged effective by the members of the environmental agencies involved in the PERIVALLON European project [27] for the sake of accelerating their landfill inspection processes.

DroneWaste also contains instance-level segmentation masks and thus can be used to train DL models for more advanced image recognition tasks, such as instance segmentation and semantic segmentation. Employing a segmentation approach could improve the site analysis by enabling the quantification of the area covered by waste for a better assessment of the environmental impact.

Finally, future research directions may exploit uncommon waste categories included in the dataset to explore zero-shot or few-shot approaches in which DL models learn to recognize waste materials using only a limited number of samples and properly crafted prompts.

6 Data Availability

The DroneWaste dataset employed in the study is openly available in a Zenodo repository at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17045558> (accessed on 26 September 2025).

7 Code Availability

The data processing and model training tools are publicly released at <https://github.com/lucamora/dronewaste>. The GitHub repository contains the following tools:

- *Dataset analysis*: Jupyter notebook to compute and visualize general dataset statistics.
- *Model training*: scripts implementing the training routines for YOLOv8, YOLOv12, and Faster R-CNN using the proposed k-fold strategy.
- *Evaluation script*: Jupyter notebook to evaluate model performance using the proposed k-fold strategy.

The repository contains more details about training parameters and implementation details. Documentation about installation steps and training procedures is also provided.

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Author Contributions

All authors contributed to the study design, dataset development, and manuscript writing. Data preparation, visualization, and technical validation were carried out by L.M., A.D., T.P., E.T., G.K. and supervised by G.B., E.B.K., P.F., A.C.K.

Competing Interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

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